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Spatial Patterns of Literacy Differentials in Hadauti Region: A Regional Perspective

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Abstract

Literacy is an important demographic element of the human process. It is essential for a human character, social and economic development. It contributes to better health, higher productivity, higher income, capability and esteemed living, increased participation in community life. Education includes new ideas for better building of the society and their personal life style. Urban-rural differences are essentially a function of the differential rates of change occurring in towns and villages. Literacy, like other innovations, originates in urban places and diffuses subsequently into the countryside.

The present work is an attempt to study the patterns and their differentials (Male-female and urban- rural) of literacy in Hadauti region of Rajasthan. It sustains about 3720433 population but literacy rate is marginally above the state average. The study is based on data from the census of India 2011. The unit of study is tehsil. The male –female, rural –urban and general – SC, ST differentials have been worked out. The literacy rate of Hadauti region was 67.82 percent in 2011. The study aims to find out differential index and composite index of literacy development in Hadauti region. Moreover, there are remarkable gaps between male and female and between urban and rural rates in the region.

Key words: *Literacy, Differentials, Differential Index, Hadauti, Composite Index*

Introduction

Literacy or education, in the present-day context, is the single most important means of achieving a sustained improvement in well-being and a critical invasive instrument for bringing about social, economic and political inclusion and a durable integration of people particularly those 'excluded' from the mainstream of any society. It is also the important means for individuals to improve personal endowments, build capability levels, overcome constraints and enlarge their available set of opportunities and choices for a sustained development.

Literacy and Education are considered as the main driving force of development for a nation. The future of the largest democracy in India will mostly depend on people's educational development. According to Mahatma Gandhi, the purpose of education is to establish a non-violent, non-exploitative, social and economic order. Education is a highway to that goal. Keeping in this view of this accepted fact there has been a major thrust on education since independence; but as far as earning quality in India is concerned it has always been one of the biggest challenges for the government (Som and Mishra, 2014).

According to Indian Census definition "Literacy means "a person who can read and write a simple message in any language with understanding is considered literate". Literacy rates in India are calculated excluding 0-6 age group of the population. There is no denying the fact that India is still in the midst of its literacy transition. Consequently, the country is characterized by low but improving literacy rates.

A number of studies have documented, both theoretically and empirically, the importance of education not only for economic benefits but social too. Hazra (1997) has compared the performance of major regions in female literacy of the world and highlighted the low position of the South-Asian countries realm in this regard. Discussing the pattern of female literacy in India, the author pointed out that the vicious circle of female illiteracy, poverty and low status in society needs to be broken down. In his district-wise Census data based detailed study on "Spatial dimensions of literacy in India" Gosal (2001) points out that there has been not much change in the regional patterns of literacy in the country during 1961-2001. However, the rural-urban and male-female differential in literacy rates has narrowed down considerably over these years. The male-female differential in literacy rate showed significant inverse correlation with general literacy rate.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to:

- Highlight the spatial pattern of literacy;
- Analyze the literacy rates and male-female differentials
- To examine the urban-rural literacy and its differentials in the study area

- To study the differentials of SC, ST population and
- To measure the real development of literacy in the study area.

All this has been done in reference to Hadauti at tehsil level. The tehsil wise data of literacy by religion, caste, age is neither published nor made available. Therefore, the present study is restricted to the analysis of regional aspects of literacy differentials by area, residence, and sex. It is hoped that such a study shall provide an insight into the levels and regional disparities in terms of horizontal as well as vertical inequalities in literacy. We need to understand all this for planning for all-round development of the people of the region.

Methodology

The tehsil has been considered the most appropriate unit of study. The study is based primarily on the secondary data obtained from a variety of authentic government sources. The tehsil level data for totals, males, females, the rural and urban population has been taken from Census of India (2011) General Population Totals, Primary Census Abstract, Rajasthan.

For measuring the differentials or inequality in the literary rates of two relevant population groups, different scholars have employed different techniques. Gosal (1964) calculated the differential by getting the ratio between the two groups. Chitnis (1974), Banerjee (1975) Nain (1988) used the simple technique by subtracting the one variable from another. Naik (1971), Sen (1973), Krishan and Shyam (1978) and Raza and Aggarwal (1986) have also devised new techniques for calculating differentials. The following formula as used by Krishan and Shyam has been used in the present analysis.

$$DI = \frac{X_2 - X_1}{T}$$

Where, DI = Differential Index

X_2 = Literacy Percentage of Males, Urban population

X_1 = Literacy Percentage of Females, Rural population

T = Literacy Percentage of total population

To measure the real development of literacy following formula is used.

$$\text{Composite Index of Development} = \frac{\text{Total Literacy Rate}}{\text{M-F differentials} + \text{R-U differentials} + \text{Caste differentials}}$$

Study Area

Hadauti region is a part of Rajasthan state of India. The entire district of Bundi, the whole of Kota district except Ramganjmandi tehsil, Khanpur tehsil of Jhalawar district, entire Baran district except Chabra, Kishanganj and Shahbad tehsils of S-E Rajasthan forms the

Hadauti region. The name of the region derives from the Hada Rajputs, a branch of the Chauhan Rajput clan. As early as the 12th century, these Hada Rajputs migrated into this region. Hada Rao Deva, a member of this Hada Rajputs group, occupied Bundi in the year 1241, and then Kota in the year

Spatial Pattern of General Literacy Rate

Table 1 Pattern of SC, ST Literacy Rates in Hadauti

S.N.	Tehsils	SC Population 2011			ST Population 2011		
		Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
1	Atru	62.26	77.04	46.18	66.06	81.15	49.87
2	Anta	63.45	78.08	47.33	71.12	85.55	56.04
3	Baran	66.32	80.29	51.31	68.83	83.35	52.92
4	Bundi	57.75	71.32	43.13	49.43	63.76	33.86
5	Chhipabarod	57.66	73	41.29	54.67	70.7	37.53
6	Digod	65.28	79.06	50.6	73.26	88.08	57.43
7	Hindoli	47.99	61.93	37.39	53.04	68.77	36.02
8	Indragarh	63.48	79.74	46.08	63.21	81.12	43.45
9	K Patan	59.38	73.84	43.94	67.4	83.47	50.13
10	Khanpur	60.59	76.34	43.34	66.93	83.59	48.85
11	Ladpura	71.7	82.54	59.93	64.12	74.5	52.08
12	Mangrol	62.33	77.68	46.04	69.77	84.28	54.23
13	Nainwan	54.26	70.07	37.27	54.42	73.4	33.4
14	Pipalda	61.55	76.73	45.15	71.73	86.83	55.6
15	Sangod	62.78	77.38	47.33	67.28	81.53	52.02

Source: Computed by authors

1264. The area lies between 24°25'N to 25°51'N and 75°15'E to 76°45'E covering an area of 14481.6 sq.kms. The northern and southwestern boundaries are formed by Sawai Madhopur, Tonk, Bhilwara, and Chittorgarh districts of Rajasthan. The region consists of 15 administrative units that are tehsils and according to the 2011 census, it has a population of 3720433 persons out of which 40.4% is urban and 59.6% is rural.

Scheduled Caste (SC) Literacy:

Hindoli tehsil has the lowest Scheduled Caste (Map 1) literacy rate in the region and is also the backward tehsil in terms of socio-economic development. Nainwan tehsil has also lower SC literacy rates. Ladpura tehsil which is the seat of Kota city has the highest SC literacy rates. In female SC literacy rates, both Hindoli and Nainwan are almost same with slight variations, though Nainwan has

Map 1: Percentage of S.C. Literacy

the lowest female SC literacy rates. In other tehsils, though female SC literacy rates are comparatively better but the picture is not good, only Digod, Baran, and Ladpura tehsils have female SC literacy rates over 50%. Males have surpassed females in literacy in all the tehsils. The social taboo of untouchability and practice of child marriages among SC population are the reasons of low female literacy rates.

Scheduled Tribe (ST) Literacy

Bundi tehsil has the lowest Scheduled Tribe

(Map 2) literacy rate in the region. Bundi tehsil is predominantly occupied by Bhil and Meena tribes. While Meenas have good enrollment in the schools and are aware of the Government measures for their' upliftment, the Bhils lack behind as they are poor and are basically mine laborers and have no interest in education. Male ST literacy is comparatively better than their SC counterparts but the picture of female ST literacy though better is below 40% in 4 tehsils of Bundi, Chhipabarod, Hindoli, and Nainwan. Nainwan has the lowest female ST

Map 2: Percentage of S.T. Literacy

literacy rates. In spite of Government claims and measures to uplift the weaker sections of the society, the female ST literacy rates are alarmingly low. The practice of child marriages among ST population is one of the reasons of low female literacy rates.

Male-Female differentials in Literacy

There were large regional variations in terms of the male-female differential in literacy rate. At the regional level, the male-female differential is 0.41 (Table 2). It is maximum in Nainwan 0.58 while it is lowest 0.19 in the Ladpura tehsil. They are categorized into 4 groups as shown in map 4.

Table 2 Male-Female and Urban-Rural Differential Index

S.N.	Tehsil	Male Literacy %	Female Literacy %	Urban Literacy %	Rural Literacy %	Urban Literacy Differential	Male-Female Differential Index
1.	Atru	83.75	54.74	74.18	68.79	0.08	0.42
2.	Anta	84.69	56.66	78.1	68.58	0.13	0.39
3.	Baran	86.75	62.92	80.25	69.07	0.15	0.32
4.	Bundi	75.95	50.34	80.07	56.93	0.36	0.4
5.	Chippabarod	76.14	44.27	80.37	58.18	0.37	0.53
6.	Digod	84.59	57.52	NIL	71.51	0	0.38
7.	Hindoli	68.58	38.13	22.36	54.15	0.59	0.56
8.	Indergarh	80.34	49.57	76.74	60.23	0.25	0.47
9.	K.Patan	81.66	53.5	76.4	64.56	0.17	0.41
10.	Khanpur	84.75	54.21	84.17	68.8	0.22	0.44
11.	Ladpura	88.52	73.02	82.58	68.44	0.17	0.19
12.	Mangrol	84.13	55.26	75.95	68.4	0.11	0.41
13.	Nainwan	73.91	40.48	75.38	55.86	0.34	0.58
14.	Peepalda	81.26	52.35	NIL	67.3	0	0.43
15.	Sangod	84.07	56.5	78.98	69.62	0.13	0.39
	Hadauti	81.27	53.3	74.27	64.69	0.14	0.41

Source: Computed by authors

In the first category, tehsils with differential more than 0.45 are included. These form the very high differential areas. On the map, these areas are located in the north and the southern regions. The tehsils in this group are Nainwan, Hindoli, Indergarh and Chippabarod. The second category is the high differential index. It includes tehsils with differentials between 0.40 and 0.45. There are six tehsils in this which are Bundi, Keshorai Patan, Peepalda, Mangrol, Atru, and

Khanpur. These are visible in pairs on the map 3. Out of these differential indices of Keshorai Patan and Mangrol is at par with that of Hadauti region while that of Bundi is less than the region's average. Rest 3 tehsils have more than the region's average, while literacy percentage of Peepalda is less than the region's average.

The third category comprises of moderate differential areas with indices between 0.35 and 0.40. These tehsils are

visible in the center of the map and they are Anta, Digod and Sangod. The last category is of the low differential with the indices less than 0.35. It includes Baran and Ladpura tehsils. The reason for this high literacy rate are:

- These tehsils have high urbanization
- Availability of better educational facilities

in the town and cities.

- Higher awareness about the literacy among urban people.
- The greater functional necessity of literacy for employment and lesser utility of children for parent's occupation in urban areas.

Map 3: Male-Female Differentials in literacy

The inequality in literacy by sex is the outcome of traditional prejudices against female education because it is considered as having little economic value since there are strong prejudices against their employment. Female children suffer neglect and they are also not permitted much mobility and may not be sent to a school even in an adjoining village.

Urban-Rural differentials in literacy

At the regional level, the urban-rural

differential index value in literacy is 0.14 (Table 2). Like the male-female differential, the urban-rural differential also varies from one part of the region to another from 0.37 in Cippabarod to 0 in Peepalda and Digod tehsils. On the basis of variations in index values, the tehsils in the state can be grouped into four categories (map 4).

In the first category tehsils with differential index, more than 0.35 are included. These are areas of the very high

Map 4: Urban - Rural Literacy Differentials

differential which comprise of 2 tehsils viz., Chippabarod and Bundi. In the second category of high differential index values from 0.20 to 0.35, there are 3 tehsils namely, Nainwan, Indergarh, and Khanpur. All these tehsils have differential index above the regional value of 0.14.

The third category comprises of moderate differential areas with indices from 0.05 to 0.20. There are 7 tehsils in this group comprising Atru, Anta, Mangrol, Baran, Keshorai Patan, Ladpura, and Sangod. Out of these differentials of Atru, Anta, Mangrol, and Sangod are less than the regional average. The fourth category is the low differential index with values less than 0.05. In this category 3 tehsil viz., Hindoli, Peepalda, and Digod are included. Of these 3 tehsils, Hindoli's one village Dalepura has come under the Bundi towns' municipal boundary

while the other two have no urban population. In the tehsils with higher differential index values, the percentage of literacy is high in both urban and rural areas. The main factors responsible for very high and high differentials are the difference in levels of urbanization, primarily agricultural economy, a high concentration of socio-economically backward sections of the society and inadequate educational infrastructure.

Literacy Development based on Composite Index

The simple literacy rate of a district or state cannot be the real measure of literacy development because within this simplified data there are different types of differentials, like Male-Female differentials, Rural- Urban differentials and Caste differentials etc. It is

Table 3 Composite Index of Literacy Development in Hadauti Region – 2011

S.N.	Tehsil	Total Literacy	M-F Difference	R-U Difference	Lit Difference between General Class and SC+ST	Composite Index of development
1	Digod	71.51	27.07	0	4.83	2.24
2	Peepalda	67.3	28.91	0	1.69	2.21
3	Ladpura	81.71	15.5	14.14	14.83	1.84
4	Mangrol	70.18	28.87	7.55	6.42	1.64
5	Atru	69.79	29.01	5.39	9.68	1.58
6	Anta	71.18	28.03	9.52	7.76	1.57
7	Sangod	70.72	27.57	9.36	9.47	1.52
8	K.Patan	68.05	28.16	11.84	9.48	1.38
9	Baran	75.27	23.83	11.18	12.55	1.28
10	Khanpur	70.04	30.54	15.37	9.87	1.26
11	Nainwan	57.83	33.43	19.52	-1.45	1.12
12	Indergarh	65.54	30.77	16.51	12	1.11
13	Bundi	63.6	25.61	23.14	14.56	1.01
14	Chippabarod	60.67	31.87	22.19	8.04	0.98
15	Hindoli	53.92	30.45	-31.79	-12.74	-3.83

Source: Computed by authors

believed that where the difference is high, the development is low. For example, in ideal condition Male and Female literacy should be equal or near to equal in any developed area. Keeping in mind this concept we

calculate the composite development index taking the total literacy in one hand, on the other hand, Male-Female differentials, Rural-Urban Differentials, and Caste differentials are incorporated using the formula,

$$\text{Composite Index of Development} = \frac{\text{Total Literacy Rate}}{M - F \text{ differentials} + R - U \text{ differentials} + \text{Caste differentials}}$$

So, high values of the composite index means higher literacy development and lower the values means lower literacy development. In Table 3 (Map-5) tehsils are arranged in descending order according to the index value. Digod is in top position and Hindoli is in the bottom.

It has been observed in the table that Digod and Peepalda have gained top positions because they don't have urban population. It is amazing to see that 2 tehsils of Nainwan and Hindoli have better literacy among SC and ST population than general class. Due to low disparities of literacy among male-female, rural-urban and caste the tehsils like Ladpura stands in the front line but the tehsils like Baran ranked 9th even though the literacy rank of this district is 2nd.

Conclusion

Though there is an increase in the literacy of the Hadauti region but it is still low compared to the other parts of the state. There is a vast difference in the male and female literacy rates of urban and rural areas. In rural areas, parents are biased against female education and poverty also hinders girls' education.

In the socio-economically backward tehsils of the region like Hindoli, girls are made to assist their parents in the collection of farm produce (especially vegetables as this is the major agricultural produce of the area) while in Nainwan girls are given responsibility to

graze cattle.

Looking at the map of a composite index of literacy development, the government should pay special attention to Hindoli tehsil which is easily visible on the map. The statistical analysis reveals that low urban-rural differential in literacy is a characteristic of areas marked by a relatively high degree of urbanization, literacy rate, educational facilities, medical facilities, commercialization of agriculture and dense road network. The tehsils having a low level of development like Hindoli should be given top priority so that they may come up at par with developed areas, and the concept of planning with social justice is proved successful.

Therefore, in order to achieve the goal of universalization of education, more stress should be given on female literacy. The differential in literacy by sex has to be narrowed down. Financial assistance should be granted to the weaker sections of the society in order to raise their socio-economic conditions, especially in the country sides. The local bodies, NGOs, and voluntary organizations have to be invited in this regard. So, any literacy program cannot be a success without poverty eradication program. It should not only be the task of government but each and every section of the society should be involved in such programs.

Map 5: Composite Index of Literacy Development

References

- Banerjee, M. (1975), "Literacy in Singhbum, Bihar", *Geographical Review of India*, 37, 2, pp. 151-157.
- Bhardwaj, P.D. (1999): "Literacy in Himachal Pradesh", *Population Geography*, 21 (1&2), pp.31-41.
- Chandna, R.C. (1972): "Scheduled Caste Population in Rural Haryana: A Geographic Analysis", *National Geographical Journal of India*, 18(3&4), pp. 177 -186.
- Chitnis, S. (1974), *Literacy and Educational Enrolment among Scheduled Caste of Maharashtra*, Tata Institute of Social Science, Bombay.
- Dutta, G. (1982), "Analysis of literacy rates in the southern districts of West Bengal", *Geographical Review of India*, Vol. 44, No.32, pp. 19-26.
- Gosal, G.S. (1964): "Literacy in India-An Interpretative Study", *Rural Sociology*, 29(September), pp.261- 77.
- Gosal, R.P.S. (2001), "Sex composition of

- India's population, 2001: A geographical analysis," Population Geography, Vol. 23, No. 1 & 2, pp. 29-40
- Hazra, Jayanti (1997): 'Women and Literacy', Geographical Review of India, Vol. 59, No.1, March, pp. 62-74.
- Joshi, H. (2000): "Changing Literacy Levels in Rajasthan: A Geographical Analysis", Geographical Review of India, 62(2), pp.150-160.
- Kaur, B. (2013): "Profile of Literacy Disparities in Rajasthan: 2011", Population Geography, 35(1&2), pp.31-48.
- Krishan, G. and Chandna, R.C. (1974), "Haryana: Working force and its occupational structure," Manpower Journal, Vol. 10, pp. 50-72.
- Krishan, G. and Shayam, M. (1978): "Regional Aspects of Urban-Rural Differentials in Literacy in India", The Journal of Developing Areas, 13(1), pp.11-22.
- Naik, J.P. (1971), Education of the Scheduled Castes (1965-66), Occasional Monograph 6, ICSSR, New Delhi.
- Nain, N.S. (1988), Trends in Urban-Rural Differentials in Select Aspects of Indian Demography, 1951-81: A Spatial View, An Unpublished M. Phil. Dissertation, Department of Geography, Panjab University, Chandigarh.
- Nath, V. (2001), "First results of the decennial census of population: 2001," Population Geography, Vol. 23, No. 1 & 2, pp. 41-48.
- Raza, M. and Aggarwal, Y.P. (1986), "Inequalities in the levels of literacy in India: The regional dimensions," in M. Shafi and Mehdi, Raza (eds.), Spectrum of Modern Geography, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, pp. 193-226.
- Reddy, U. B. (1985), "Regional disparities in educational development in India: An inter-state analysis," Geographical Review of India, Vol. 47, No. 2, pp. 22-27.
- Sagar, P. (1991), "Regional disparities in literacy of India 1981," Asian Profile, Vol. 19, No. 3, pp. 253-66.
- Shafiqullah, S. (2011): "Regional Analysis of Urban-Rural Differentials in Literacy in Uttar Pradesh, India", Journal of Geography and Regional Planning, 4(5), pp.287 -296.
- Siddique, M. (1977): "The Geography of Literacy in Uttar Pradesh", Geographical Review of India, 39(1), pp.374-388.
- Singh, C.P. (1979), "Literacy in a rural population in Meerut District," Geographical Observer, Vol. 15, pp. 32-36.
- Som, K.S. and Mishra, R.P (2014), "Gender Imbalance: Trends, Pattern and its Impact on West Bengal", International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication, Vol.4, issue7, Pp.1-1

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